

Epic of Gilgamesh

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Entry tags: Excavated text, Epic, Near East, Babylonian Text, Sumerian religions, Text, Assyrian Religions, Religious Group, Mesopotamian Religions

The Epic of Gilgamesh is a Babylonian narrative poem that recounts the adventures of the eponymous King Gilgamesh, the legendary ruler of the city state of Uruk. Stories about Gilgamesh were told from at least the 21st century BCE to the second century CE in a variety of formats, including a Sumerian cycle of poems, an epic poem in Akkadian, prose versions in Hittite and Hurrian, and visual depictions, not to mention oral retellings that have not survived in the archeological record. The Babylonian epic developed continuously from the early second to the early first millennium BCE. Scholars recognize three main phases: an Old Babylonian epic that is imperfectly preserved; a Middle Babylonian phase of revision and experimentation; and an edited version in the Standard Babylonian language, composed around the 11th century BCE. The latter version, consisting of twelve Tablets (the twelfth of which forms an appendix to the main narrative of the first eleven), is the best-preserved and best-known account of Gilgamesh's story. The epic can be divided into two parts, the first of which tells of Gilgamesh's love and triumphs, the second of his loss and failures. Gilgamesh is a restless, tyrannic king in Uruk, and the gods send the wild man Enkidu to befriend and distract him. The two become close friends, possibly lovers, and set off on a series of heroic adventures, killing the monster Humbaba and the Bull of Heaven. But halfway through the epic, Enkidu dies, and the second half of the story relates Gilgamesh's profound grief and his ultimately futile attempt to achieve immortality.

Date Range: 1900 BCE - 130 BCE

Region: Tell Warka3

Region tags: West Asia, Southern Iraq

The remains of the city state of Uruk

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Andrew George, 2003. *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic: Introduction, Critical Edition, and Cuneiform Texts*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Source 2: Sophus Helle, 2021. *Gilgamesh: A New Translation of the Ancient Epic*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Source 3: Martin Worthington, 2019. *Ea's Duplicity in the Gilgamesh Flood Story*. London: Routledge

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.soas.ac.uk/baplar/recordings/>

– Source 1 Description: Recordings of how leading scholars believe that the Epic of Gilgamesh (and other texts) may have sounded

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.soas.ac.uk/gilgamesh/standard/>

– Source 1 Description: Score (synoptic) edition of the Standard Babylonian Epic of Gilgamesh

– Source 2 URL: https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/etcsl.cgi?text=c.1.8.1*#

– Source 2 Description: Translations and transliterations of the Sumerian stories about Gilgamesh

– Source 3 URL: <https://seal.huji.ac.il/index.php/taxonomy/term/89>

– Source 3 Description: Translations and transliterations of the Old Babylonian Gilgamesh

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Method of inscription

– Other [specify]: Stylus

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Clay object

– Clay tablet

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: There were lineages associated with Gilgamesh, as formulated e.g. in the Sumerian King List. The Epic mentions that he is the son of the king Lugal-Banda and (more importantly) of the goddess Ninsun, but does not provide a full lineage of Gilgamesh's ancestors or descendants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The primary evidence for a spirit-body distinction in Gilgamesh comes from the visions of the Netherworld presented in Tablets VII and XII, where disembodied spirits are said to reside in the Netherworld.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Cremation?

– No

Notes: Cremation is implicitly condemned in Tablet XII, as it destroys the spirit of the dead.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Mummification?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Notes: In Tablet XII, leaving a corpse unburied is depicted as a terrible outcome.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Notes: Humbaba threatens to feed Gilgamesh and Enkidu to the birds and insects, but this is a threat, not proper funerary practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

Notes: Secondary burial was practiced in Mesopotamia, but is not addressed in the epic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human sacrifices present?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present?

– Yes

Notes: A long but fragmentary section in Tablet VIII details the mortuary sacrifices that accompany the burial of Enkidu, including meat offered to the Underworld gods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: A long but fragmentary section in Tablet VIII details the mortuary sacrifices that accompany the burial of Enkidu.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Personal effects?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

|

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

Notes: Enkidu is buried under the Euphrates river, but a lavish statue to him is erected in Uruk

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In cemetery?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

|

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: According to tradition (and presumably the fragmentary section at the end of Tablet VIII), Enkidu and then Gilgamesh were buried under the Euphrates river, which was diverted for this purpose.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: This is the case in other Babylonian and Assyrian sources, but not in the Epic of Gilgamesh

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Notes: In the Epic of Gilgamesh, Enlil is berated at length by the other gods for causing the Flood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
- Yes
- Notes: Enlil does not know e.g. that Uta-napishti is building the boat, so his knowledge is restricted, but the nature of that restriction is unclear
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
- Yes
- Notes: See above
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
- No
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
- No
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
- Field doesn't know
- Notes: It might be *possible* for Enlil to see anyone at any time, but it is clear that he does not actually see everyone at every time (see above).
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
- Field doesn't know
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Tell Warka
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
- Yes

Notes: In Tablet V, Enkidu considers the possibility that Enlil will examine the heroes' motives for destroying the Cedar Forest.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Again, the knowledge is restricted, but in ways that are unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Notes: Though Enlil exhibits positive emotions in other Sumerian and Babylonian texts, his emotions are almost exclusively negative in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

Notes: During the Flood, the gods (including Enlil) are starved by the absence of sacrifices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Notes: It may be possible to hurt Enlil, but this is not related in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can be tricked?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Notes: It may be possible to hurt Enlil, but this is not related in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Notes: Other gods, including Shamash and Istar, are shown in the Epic of Gilgamesh to communicate with humans in everyday life, but Enlil only communicates with Uta-napishti at the end of the Flood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In dreams

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not clear which god exactly sends the dreams seen by Gilgamesh: the only explicit sender of a dream is Ea, who reveals the coming Flood to Uta-napishti in a dream. Enlil also appears in Enkidu's dream, where he sees the gods gather to decree his death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Divinatory communication with Enlil was common in Babylonian culture, but does not appear in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, Enlil meets Uta-napishti to make him immortal at the end of the story of the Flood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Enkidu sees the human spirits in the Underworld, both in his dream vision in Tablet VII and in his Underworld journey in Tablet XII.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Enkidu physically interacts with the Underworld spirits in Tablet XII.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: In other cuneiform texts, dead spirits are summoned by necromancy, but that is not the case in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Tablet XII makes clear that some Underworld spirits live a content afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Most spirits described in Tablet XII have a somewhat or very negative existence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Notes: Only in the exceptional circumstance of Enkidu's journey to the Underworld. In other cuneiform texts, dead spirits are summoned by necromancy, but that is not the case in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, the gods' knowledge appears restricted, but the nature of the restriction is unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See notes for supreme deity above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See notes for supreme deity above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: The gods are associated with specific domains, but their power does not seem to be entirely restricted to those domains.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In dreams?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Notes: In the Epic of Gilgamesh, the mixed human-divine being *is* the monarch, Gilgamesh himself.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: There are a number of "monstrous" beings, such as Humbaba, the protective guardian spirit of the Cedar Forest, and the scorpion people, who guard the gate through which the Sun God rises and sets.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: In a limited sense: when Gilgamesh's citizens pray to the gods and ask them to stop his abuses of power, the gods intervene by creating Enkidu to distract and divert him. However, the story of the Flood related in Tablet XI is not, as in the Hebrew Bible, meant to enforce prosocial norm adherence, but is caused by the gods' sleeplessness due to human noise.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: Other cuneiform sources, such as Maqlû, depict the gods punishing humans for transgressing social taboos, but these concerns are not evident from Gilgamesh.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: Only in the very limited sense that the goddess Ishtar wants to have sex with Gilgamesh, and punishes him when he rebuffs her.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Notes: Again, divine monitoring for lying (and sorcery, crimes, and slander) are evinced by other cuneiform texts, but not from Gilgamesh.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
 - Notes: Oaths appear occasionally in the Epic, most famously in the oath of silence sworn by the gods, which prevents them from revealing the coming Flood to the humans.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
 - Notes: See above
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
 - Notes: See above
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: Rituals appear several times in the epic, most commonly in the form of libations or animal sacrifices
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of temples was a major concern for Babylonian kings, and may be one of the reasons why the heroes undertake the quest to the Cedar Forest

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Typically done for revenge (e.g. Ishtar avenging Gilgamesh's insults, and the gods decreeing Enkidu's death for the heroes' killing of the two beings under their protection) or to further the gods' own interests (e.g. summoning the Flood so that the gods may sleep better).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: "Punishment" implies that adverse moral behavior in this life is met by a negative fate in the afterlife, which is not the case: one's fate in the afterlife, as depicted in Tablet XII, depends primarily on the manner of one's death and on how many descendants one leaves behind to give regular offerings of food and drink.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Notes: Most of the punishments listed here appear in other cuneiform sources, but not in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

↳ Political failure?

– No

Notes: It can in other cuneiform sources (such as the downfall of Naram-Sin), but not in the Epic of Gilgamesh.

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

Notes: See above

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

Notes: In the rather extreme sense of the Flood. More "normal" bad weather as divine punishment is also attested in other cuneiform sources.

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

Notes: See above.

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

Notes: See above

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

Notes: See above

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

Notes: See above

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Notes: See above

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

|

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

Notes: Only indirectly: Shamash rewards Ninsun's prayer by supporting Gilgamesh in battle, for example, which implicitly encourages the performance of rituals, but that is not the main purpose of the reward.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: See answer to whether punishments are meted out in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Notes: Most of the rewards listed here are found in other cuneiform texts, but not all in the Epic of Gilgamesh

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Notes: Shamash supports Gilgamesh and Enkidu in the battle against Humbaba

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Notes: The gods reward the prayers of the people of Uruk by reducing Gilgamesh's tyrannical behavior.

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the rather extreme sense that Uta-napishti is rewarded with eternal life for his actions during the Flood

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tell Warka

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The Epic does not explicitly prescribe any norms, though some norms emerge from its narrative arc—e.g. the murder of Humbaba is condemned by the gods as wrong, and Enkidu is punished as a result of it

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

Notes: The god Ea's elusiveness and deception is praised rather than condemned

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: Characters who display kindness and compassion, such as Shamhat, are displayed positively and rewarded

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: The heroes are condemned for ignoring Humbaba's pleas for mercy

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Ninsun is shown purifying herself before praying to Shamash

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: In Tablet V, the text offers a number of proverbial sayings in praise of cooperation

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Notes: Gilgamesh's constant restlessness and lack of patience often leads him to trouble, so patience may be indirectly praised

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Notes: Again, Gilgamesh's constant lack of equanimity is one of the main problems that plague him, so the Epic may be indirectly elevating this property

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The sacrifice of adults is alluded to in one of the Sumerian stories about Gilgamesh, the Death of Gilgamesh, but not in the Babylonian epic

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The Epic does not make any direct requirement, but it does present some religious behavior as desirable and expected according to the conventions of Babylonian culture, including the regular offerings and libations that the heroes make on their journeys and the valuable funerary sacrifices that Gilgamesh presents at Enkidu's funeral

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: See above—physical risk-taking is valued, but not prescribed.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: See above

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: See above

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Epic may or may not have been performed. If it was performed, it may or may not have been recited in dramatic fashion.

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: While again the Epic does not prescribe offerings, but describe the heroes' and other characters' performance of rituals, visual stimuli are an important component of that description: note the contrast between the bright blue of lapis lazuli and the dull red of carnelian in the list of funerary offerings to Enkidu

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: The maintenance of sacred spaces is specified in other cuneiform sources, but not in the Epic of Gilgamesh

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- A city-state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

- An empire

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- No

Notes: This is addressed in the epic Atra-hasis, but not in the Epic of Gilgamesh

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- Yes

Notes: Briefly, in that Gilgamesh encourages the stewards he leaves in charge of Uruk to care for the poor, and Uta-napishti urges Gilgamesh to be mindful of the wretched

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

- No

Other forms of welfare?

- Yes

Notes: A central concern in the text is the use and abuse of ilku, taxation in the form of labor that rulers were expected to employ for projects that would benefit the entire community—in the case of Gilgamesh, the mighty walls of Uruk that he builds

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- Yes

Notes: Stories about Gilgamesh were part of the school curriculum in both the second and the first millennium BCE

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

- No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: During the first millennium, educated scribes were almost exclusively male

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The text praises the acquisition of knowledge more generally, but not education in particular

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

Notes: When Ishtar releases the Bull of Heaven, she is told to first store of seven years' worth of food in Uruk

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: As noted above, the construction of the Walls of Uruk is a major feature in the legend of Gilgamesh more broadly

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– No

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Notes: See the notes on the levying of ilku-labor above

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: Humbaba's plea to be treated as a vassal ruler (and Gilgamesh's refusal of that plea) are a mythical reflection of Babylonian imperialism

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: Hunting, fishing, pastoralism, large-scale agriculture

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